











- [12] Trzcinski, T., Christoudias, M., Fua, P., & Lepetit, V. (2013, June). Boosting binary keypoint descriptors. In *Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR), 2013 IEEE Conference on* (pp. 2874-2881). IEEE.
- [13] Das, P., Ghoshal, R., Kole, D. K., & Ghosh, R. (2012). Measurement of Displacement and Velocity of a Moving Object from Real Time Video. *International Journal of Computer Applications*, 49(13).
- [14] Kanan, C., & Cottrell, G. W. (2012). Color-to-grayscale: does the method matter in image recognition. *PloS one*, 7(1), e29740.